

METHODOLOGY OF FORMING PEDAGOGICAL RESPONSIBILITY ON THE BASIS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article discusses the methodology of pedagogical responsibility formation based on the development of professional competence in future teachers.

Keywords: competence, responsibility, methodology, education, training, professional competence, modern education, professional activity, creative activity.

Introduction. What qualities of competence should future teachers highlight in themselves? What is competence itself? What is reflected in the core of competence? What is responsibility? What are its types? What are the methods of forming pedagogical responsibility through the development of professional competence? We will discuss these questions in this chapter.

In English, the word “*competence*” literally means “*ability*”. Its content is understood as the feature of highlighting “individual human potential and capabilities”.

Based on the results of psychological research and the analysis of the presented ideas, we were able to clarify the content and essence of the concept of “competence”. Psychologically, this concept is defined as “the ability of a specialist to behave in unfamiliar situations and circumstances, to build meaningful dialogue, to find new solutions to misunderstandings that arise in relationships, to use ambiguous, contradictory information, and to have a self-motivated position in consistently developing and complex processes.”

Literature review. Competence requires a specialist to constantly develop and improve knowledge, acquire new information, have a deep understanding of social relations, search for everyday information, and apply it in their activities. Thus, a specialist with professional competence deeply feels the needs of the times, strives for new knowledge, finds it, processes it, and effectively applies it in their practice.

The interrelationship and interrelated aspects of the professional competence and pedagogical responsibility of future teachers are classified as follows.

The relationship between professional competence and pedagogical responsibility

A competent approach to the process of training future teachers is aimed at their comprehensive mastery of knowledge and practical methods of activity that ensure their success in the main areas of their activities, both for their own personal interests and for their professional activities. The formation of professional qualities of future teachers is directly related to the activity of their personal and creative activity in the teaching process. The most important task of modern teaching in the higher education system is to create favorable conditions for the formation of professional awareness of future teachers. Creative activity is an activity that requires long-term preparation, erudition, and competencies.

Discussion. *At the 1st stage*, the state of reliance on professional values based on a competency-based approach to the formation of students' pedagogical responsibility was analyzed.

At the 2nd stage, a survey was conducted among teachers of higher pedagogical education. They were conducted in the following areas:

1. To determine the understanding of which competencies are priority for professors in developing a sense of responsibility in students.
2. To assess the extent to which they understand the need for a value-based approach in the formation of professional competencies that are important for a future teacher.
3. To determine the extent to which they pay attention to the high level of professional responsibility in the training of future teachers in higher education practice.

4. To study the state of teachers' purposeful approach to the development of professional responsibility and accountability in future teachers in the process of teaching subjects.

5. To determine the state of use of educational tasks aimed at increasing professional responsibility in students based on modern approaches in lessons.

6. To analyze the use of questions and tasks aimed at increasing responsibility in the development of higher education teachers as one of the criteria for effective preparation of future specialists for the profession.

– **At the 3rd stage**, questionnaires were conducted among future teachers. They reflected the following content:

– To what extent do students analyze the concept of professional responsibility;

– To what extent do students have responsibility for their chosen profession;

– To what extent do students have knowledge about professional qualities such as responsibility, freedom, duty, responsibility, conscience;

– The degree to which students have formed professional qualities;

– The degree to which students have formed their attitude towards completing tasks that express professional responsibility skills;

– Students' responsible approach to the process of completing tasks;

– Feeling of responsibility towards their teachers and teammates;

– The study and analysis of such problems as conscientious participation in socio-political processes taking place in society and loyalty to duty were reflected.

– At stage 4, the results of the preliminary survey were analyzed.

– Pedagogical responsibility is the responsibility of the teacher in the formation of knowledge, skills and upbringing of students in the educational process. Pedagogical responsibility includes the following aspects:

– 1. Professionalism: The teacher's use of modern methods and technologies in his work, the ability to correctly convey knowledge.

– 2. Ethics: The teacher's attitude towards students, the organization of a communication process taking into account their personal characteristics.

– 3. Self-development: The teacher's regular assessment of his activities and increasing his effectiveness.

– 4. Responsibility: Responsibility for the results of high-quality education of students.

– 5. Creativity: Development of new and effective teaching methods.

– Pedagogical responsibility determines the role and influence of the teacher in the educational process. It plays an important role in shaping the future of students. There are a number of pedagogical features of pedagogical responsibility, which are as follows:

– *Teacher influence*: The teacher influences students through his knowledge and skills. He helps students form and develop as individuals.

– *Ethical responsibility*: Teachers should follow ethical standards, be fair and consistent in educating students.

– *Psychological responsibility*: Teachers should understand the psychological state of students and support them. This helps students understand themselves and develop.

- *Individuality of the educational process:* Each student has his own characteristics, so the teacher should plan and implement the educational process individually.
- *Responsibility for results:* The teacher takes responsibility for the successes and difficulties of students in their studies. They analyze the results of students and take the necessary measures.
- *Innovation in teaching and education:* Teachers should strive to use new methods and technologies to increase student interest and improve the quality of education.
- *Collaboration and teamwork:* There is a responsibility to develop cooperation between teachers, parents and other educational staff, as this affects the success of students.

Conclusion. These characteristics constitute the main aspects of pedagogical responsibility and play an important role in the educational process. In conclusion, there is a need for systematic work to increase professional competence and sense of responsibility among teachers, from teachers working in schools to professors working in the higher education system, and especially among future teachers.

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